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EVALUATION OF LEPIDIUM SATIVUM SEED MUCILAGE AS A BINDER IN TABLET FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the current study was to extract the mucilage from Garden Cress (*Lepidium Sativum* Linn) seeds and to investigate the compressional behavior of mucilage in tablet formulation in comparison with standard binder such as starch using Heckel and Kawakita plot. Using paracetamol as model drug granules was prepared with different concentration (1%, 2%, and 3%) of the mucilage and starch by wet granulation method. The granules and tablets were evaluated for their flow properties, hardness, weight variation, thickness etc., and found to have hardness and disintegration time slightly more compared to starch as binder and hence satisfactory to prepare compressed tablets. The study revealed that the *Lepidium sativum* mucilage compared favourably with the standard starch as binder but plasticity of starch is more than *Lepidium sativum* mucilage as binder.

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INTRODUCTION

To improve the flow properties of powders, binders are used in tablet formulation to exert cohesion between the powder mixes so as to form granules. The quantity of binder and the method of compression used have considerable influence on the characteristics of the compressed tablets.

Due to eco friendly, biodegradable and compatible nature of Plant based natural excipients are more preferred over synthetic excipients. Binders such as natural gums and mucilage's are biocompatible, cheap, and easily available and have advantage of lack of toxicity, low cost.²

The objective of the study is to evaluate the *lepidium Sativum* mucilage for its tablet binding properties.¹ *Lepidum sativum* is an annual herb, belonging to the family Brassicacea family. It is a fast growing, edible plant botanically related to watercress and mustard and sharing their peppery tangy flavor and aroma. Seeds, leaves and roots are economically important, however crop is mainly cultivated for seeds.²⁻³ During the compression of the material compressional properties of its material is important, volume reduction mechanism of the material are evaluated using the mathematical equations (eg. Heckel and Kawakita)⁴⁻⁶

$$\text{Heckel equation: } \ln [1/(1-Dr)] = KP + A$$

Where,

dr = relative density

A= constant (intercept of the linear portion of the plot which is the function of original compact volume indicates the degree of densification by particle rearrangement)

P = applied pressure 'p'

The slope of the linear regression is the Heckel constant K, a material dependent parameter inversely proportional to mean yield pressure.

$$\text{Kawakita equation: } N/C = [(1/a) N, 1/ab$$

Where,

N is the tapping number, C is the degree of volume reduction and a and b are constants. C in equation vi is given by;

$$C = [V_o - V_N] / V_o$$

Lepidum sativum have been commonly used to treat a variety of disorders in Ayurvedic system of medicine all over India. Mucilages are usually byproducts of metabolism, formed within the cell in plants. The present study focus on the analysis of nature of the mucilage as binder relative to standard binder starch using heckle and Kawakita Plots.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Paracetamol is a gift sample provided by Centaur Pharmaceuticals Ltd, Pune, India. All the other chemicals, solvents, reagents used were of analytical grade. The seeds of *Lepidum Sativum* were obtained from local market

Extraction of mucilage from seeds:

About 100 gm of *lepidium Sativum* seeds were soaked in 800 ml of water for 12 hours. The soaked seeds were blended for 15 mins. At about 2000 rpm using homogenizer. The blended seeds were then filtered through muslin cloth. Additional 200 ml of water was added to the seeds and again blended and refiltered through muslin cloth. To the filtrate 800 ml equivalent amount of acetone was added to allow to precipitate the mucilage. White supernatant mass separates after precipitation by acetone. Precipitated mucilage was then spread on glass slab and dried in tray drier at the temperature not exceeding 60oc for 16 hrs. Dried mucilage easily separates in the form of flakes on the slab by spraying acetone over dried mucilage.²

Preparation and evaluation of granules:

The granules of paracetamol were prepared by wet granulation method using *Lepidum sativum* mucilage and starch binder in the concentration of 1%, 2%, 3% as shown in table 1. The paracetamol powder, lactose, sodium starch glycolate, talc and magnesium stearate were carefully weighed. All the powdered ingredients were dry mixed manually in mortar to give uniform mix. Small amount of binder solutions were prepared by dissolving the appropriate weights of binder in small quantity of distilled water in a beaker. Binder solution were slowly added to the mixture. The dump mass was granulated by passing them through 16 number mesh. Granules were dried at 60oc. The granules were evaluated for angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and hausner ratio. Change in the volume after small number of tapping was recorded to calculate Kawakita parameters⁵⁻⁷.

Table no.1 Formulation of Paracetamol tablets:

Formulation code →	F0 (0%)	F1 (1%)	F2 (2%)	F3 (3%)	F4 (1%)	F5 (2%)	F6 (3%)
Paracetamol	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
LSM(Binder)	-	1% (q.s)	2% (q.s)	3% (q.s)	-	-	-
Starch	-	-	-	-	1% (q.s)	2% (q.s)	3% (q.s)
Lactose	156	156	156	156	156	156	156
Sodium Starch Glycolate	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Magnesium stearate	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Talc	6	6	6	6	6	6	6

Preparation and evaluation of tablets:

After evaluation granules were compressed into tablets at various pressure (0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 7 tons) to study the compressional behavior using KBr press having punch diameter 12mm. the tablets were evaluated for thickness, diameter, and hardness. Heckel Parameters were calculated by using change in volume of the tablet with pressure to calculate the density at each compressional pressure⁸⁻¹⁰

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of granules flow properties revealed that granules possess good flow properties and could be used for further compression into tablet. As Shown in table 2 the physical properties of granules and tablet containing various concentration of mucilage and starch as binder that hardness and disintegration time increases with the increase in the binder concentration. this increase indicates the formation of stronger bonds. Compacts containing Lepidium Sativum mucilage as binder were less friable than those with starch.

Table no.2 Evaluation of granules for flow properties.

Binder	Form code	Conc Binder (%)	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped Density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner ratio	Angle repose	of Friability (%)	Hardness	Disintegration Time
No binder	F0	0	0.412	0.530	22.22	1.21	23.49	crumbled	2.56	0.5 min
Mucilage	F1	1	0.52	0.65	19.72	1.18	29.70	0.49	3.72	1min 25sec
	F2	2	0.48	0.63	14.89	1.12	30.04	0.46	4.60	1 min 42 sec
	F3	3	0.47	0.58	13.37	1.14	28.70	0.42	5.56	1 min 45 sec
Starch	F4	1	0.44	0.62	13.40	1.13	30.52	0.49	3.87	1 min 30 sec
	F5	2	0.48	0.69	13.74	1.12	30.43	0.44	3.68	1 min 33 sec
	F6	3	0.40	0.60	20.47	1.10	30.32	0.47	3.51	1 min 41 sec

Table no. 3 Parameters obtained from Kawakita plot.

Binder	formulation	Conc.Of binder(%)	1/ab	a	1/b	1/a
Mucilage	F0	0	6.524	0.302	20.56	8.2365
	F1	1	2.261	0.217	18.41	6.607
	F2	2	2.281	0.152	10.51	5.547
	F3	3	4.610	0.189	14.39	4.2907
Starch	F4	1	2.985	0.218	19.85	2.7976
	F5	2	4.201	0.232	14.89	4.5854
	F6	3	3.278	0.357	17.08	4.30511

Compressional characteristics:

Fig. 1 and 2 show representative kawakita plots for paracetamol formulations containing different % of binders.

Fig.1 Kawakita plot for Mucilage as binder.

Fig. 2 Kawakita plot for starch as binder.

"a" value indicates total reduction in the volume of powder bed. "b" value is inversely proportional to yield strength of particles. With increase in the value of compressibility "b" value goes on increasing. If the value of "b" is more, it means yield strength is less and hence good compressibility. In fig.2 relationship between N/C and N was obtained. However, degree of volume reduction c, changes with change in tapping number. This initial change in C was more rapid in formulations without binder, followed by those with starch and then *Lepidium Sativum* mucilage.

The values of $1/b$ and $1/ab$ were obtained from the slopes and the intercept of the plots respectively. The tapping experiments were performed on all the samples and "a" and $1/b$ were evaluated. It is predicted that the cohesiveness of the formulation containing starch would increase because $1/b$ is large in these formulations.

Table 3 shows that $1/b$ value is higher in starch as well as in *lepidium sativum* mucilage for 1%. Formulation containing 2% of mucilage exhibited the lowest value of $1/b$ in both type of binders, indicating more value in starch binder than mucilage. Low value of $1/b$ indicates materials that are soft and that readily deform plastically under pressure.

Fig. 3 and 4 shows representative Heckel plots for paracetamol formulation of mucilage and starch as binder in different concentration. The values of P_y , D_a , D_b , and D_o for all formulation are presented in the table 4. The P_y value was calculated from the regions of the plots. The intercept a was determined from the extrapolation of the line. The D_o value, which represent the degree of initial packing in the die as a result of die filling increased as the mucilage concentration increased, but the value decreased with increase in the starch concentration. This result indicates that the formulation containing mucilage exhibited highest degree of packing in the die because of die filling.

Table no.4 Parameters obtained from Heckel plots.

Binder Type	Binder Conc. (%)	D_a	P_y	D_o	D_B
LSM	0	0.4652	23.62	0.4596	0.5118
	1	0.4472	21.63	0.49074	0.44571
	2	0.5361	21.27	0.505457	0.50123
	3	0.5411	21.18	0.523892	0.53914
Starch	1	0.4432	21.63	0.463354	0.42954
	2	0.4501	20.30	0.510141	0.424658
	3	0.4622	21.35	0.512121	0.422757

(Note- D_o - Relative density of the powdered bed at applied pressure zero, P_y -Yield pressure, D_a - Relative density, D_b - difference between D_a and D_o , A- Intercept).

Fig .3 Heckel plot for mucilage as binder.

Fig.4 Heckel plot for starch as binder.

The D_B value, which represents the particle rearrangement phase in the early compression stages and tends to indicate the extent of particle or granule fragmentation although fragmentation can occur concurrently with plastic and elastic deformation of constituent particles. The *lepidium sativum* mucilage decreased the D_b value of the granules relative to the formulation (0% binder) this implies that the extent of rearrangement of particles at low pressure was lower when compared with Starch binder. All of these would explain the fact that D_a value for *lepidium sativum* seed mucilage granules was lower relative to starch indicating lower degree of packing at zero or lower pressure, these values were observed to increase with increase in binder concentration. The D_b value of the formulation containing *lepidium sativum* seed mucilage and starch were much lower than their D_o values, suggesting that higher pressure are required for granule fragmentation. The mean yield pressure value P_y is inversely related to the formulation ability to deform plastically under the pressure. The value of P_y for formulation containing both the binders were lower than for the formulation without binder implying that the presence of binder increased the plasticity of the formulation. The P_y values for the formulation containing starch were lower than those containing *lepidium sativum* seeds except for 3% binder solution implies that the onset of plastic deformation in the formulation containing starch occurs at lower pressures. values of the formulations without binder was rather high compared to formulation with binder.

CONCLUSIONS

From the result obtained, *Lepidium sativum* mucilage compared favorably with the standard starch as a binder but plasticity of starch is slightly more than mucilage as binder as per Heckel analysis were as per Kawakita plots plasticity of mucilage is more than starch. Hence it can be concluded that compared to without binder tablet, mucilage as a binder containing tablet is showing good compression characteristics also higher mechanical strength and disintegration time of tablet suggesting that it can be used as binder in Pharmaceutical formulations.

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